

ISic3171

I.Sicily inscription 3171

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

vicinity of Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di Vigna Cassia, inventory 45

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329746

1. σω□-

2. τήρ.

3. ²ramus palmae²

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645501

PHI 329746

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 15.0586

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 259 no.2 dr

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